

SENTIMENT POLARITY CLASSIFICATION USING DISTRIBUTION POINTWISE-MUTUAL INFORMATION (D-PMI) BASED ON FUSION SENTIMNET LEXICON AND SENTIMENT PROPAGATION

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Abstract

Sentiment analysis becomes critical important to figure out the content of their reviews and to extract sentiment by providing structured and readable polarity-oriented outputs automatically. Lexicon methods commonly rely on the assumption that adjectives share the same polarities with their synonyms and opposite polarities with their antonyms manually without considering the domain-dependent and context characteristic of the sentiment lexicon. When special words is carrying a specific sentiment polarity in one domain may even indicate a different sentiment polarity in another domain or even in single domain which cannot intuitively acquire from existing general lexicon methods. To distinguish the sentiment polarity of a particular word, SentiWordNet is mostly used as general sentiment lexicon. Nevertheless, sentiment lexicons for classification by employing singular general sentiment lexicon caused inaccurate semantic scoring of particular words from different lexicons. Besides, Pointwise-mutual Information (PMI) is used to find out the semantic orientation. However, it is bias infrequent features and not effective due to the model are syntactic context of words and a list of seed word are necessary. In this paper, we aim to provide more comprehensive and fine-

grained mining results, we proposed Distribution Pointwise Mutual Information (D-PMI) based on fusion sentiment lexicon and propagation to improve the generalization capability of sentiment polarity classification. In order to achieve this, phase 1 as baseline by fusion sentiment lexicon to resolve their inconsistencies and obtain more accurate sentiment knowledge. D-PMI is used to measure association between different elements according distributions of word occurrences to avoid biased toward infrequently features. Phase 2 as improvement by sentiment propagation to extract frequency of sentiment words and sentiment relation among words to improve sentiment polarity classification.

1 INTRODUCTION

The field of sentiment analysis has received increasing attention in recent years [1]. Supervised classification performs well in predicting the sentiment polarity for a given domain, but the performance of domain-specific classifier drops drastically when it directly applied to another context domains [2]. It requires a large amount of labelled dataset to trained domain classifier for each new domain, thus moving in the direction of domain independence is lacking.

The aim of lexicon-based method is to predict the sentiment polarity using unlabeled data because it is much cheaper and easier to collect on a large scale. Currently lexicon method is using general purpose sentiment dictionaries such as SentiWordNet to classify the polarities of a particular word, but the performance level report has not been impressive. These methods commonly rely on the assumption that adjectives share the same polarities with their synonyms and opposite polarities with their antonyms without considering the domain-dependent characteristic of the sentiment lexicon [3].

Moreover, people tend to use some different words to express sentiment. Some special words are carrying a specific sentiment polarity in one domain may even indicate different sentiment polarity in another domain or even in single domain which cannot intuitively acquire from existing lexicon methods. However, Mikolov proposed to measure the association between different lexical elements but they ignore the sentiment information of texts [4]. Srishti Sharma proposed to make use of the interrelationships between words in a review document in order to evaluate their semantic relevance to a particular sentiment. Yet, it is only computed based on the physical distances of neighboring words [5]. Vinay present simple learning algorithm called Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) followed by Semantic Orientation (SO) in averaging the semantic orientation of phrase does in classification of user reviews [6]. Unfortunately, Pointwise-mutual information is biased toward infrequent features and words. This introduces limitation of words used in a wrong context or domain. Methods to employ a richer lexical resource and a better calculation of relationship between words are lacking.

Therefore, we proposed Distribution Pointwise Mutual Information (D-PMI) to measure association between different elements

according distributions of word occurrences instead of co-occurrence frequency to avoid biased toward infrequently features. Based on sentiment lexicon fusion from different sentiment lexicons to resolve their inconsistencies and obtain more accurate sentiment knowledge. Finally, sentiment propagation including conjunctions, intensification and negation also used to extract frequency of sentiment words and the sentiment interrelation among words will be computed and combined based on sentiment similarities to balance the coverage and accuracy and improve sentiment polarity classification.

2 PROPOSED WORK

We proposed sentiment polarity classification using Distribution Pointwise-mutual information (D-PMI) based on fusion sentiment lexicon and sentiment propagation in figure 1:

Figure1 Methodology of propose work.

The very first step of classification is to extract the phrases containing adverbs and adjectives in the review. Single word adjective and adverbs

may have different meaning in different context and they modify the meaning of other word quickly. Therefore, we selected unigram and bigrams containing adjective and adverb by using POS Tagging. As baseline of sentiment polarity classification in phase 1, we fusion sentiment lexicons for sentiment knowledge from three different sentiment dictionaries: SentiWordNet, Bing Liu’s lexicon and MPQA to resolve their inconsistencies and obtain more accurate general knowledge and generate the candidate sentiment words list after removing duplicates from those sentiment lexicons instead of singular existing sentiment lexicon.

We proposed Distribution Pointwise-Mutual Information (D-PMI) to measure the association between different lexical elements (unigram and bigrams). Figure 2 as below shows that the comparison between Pointwise-Mutual Information (PMI) and Distribution Pointwise-Mutual Information (D-PMI).

Pointwise-Mutual Information (PMI)	Distribution Pointwise-Mutual Information (D-PMI)
$PMI(t,s) = \log_2 \frac{P(t,s)}{P(t)P(s)}$	$D-PMI = \frac{1}{\log_2 \frac{P(w, R)}{P(w, (R, U, R_0))}}$ if $w \in L_s$
<p>$P(t,s)$ is the co-occurrence probability of t and s. $P(t)P(s)$ gives the probability that the two terms co-occur if they are statistically independent. The ratio between $P(t,s)$ and $P(t)P(s)$ is thus a measure of the degree of statistical dependence between them. The log of this ratio is the amount of information that we acquire about the presence of one of the word when we observe other. Here the t means extracted two-word phrase and s means the seed words. PMI of phrase is calculated with respect to both categories of seed words.</p>	<p>Given a set of product reviews R, R_c contain fusion sentiment lexicon s and R_c contain candidate t. V is the vocabulary where the set of words that occur in R_c, U, R_c. $P(w, R_c)$ means the probability that a randomly selected review from R_c contain word w.</p> <p>D-PMI considers the distributions of word occurrences instead of the co-occurrence frequency between different words. Thus D-PMI overcome the challenge caused by infrequent features and words.</p>
<p>Therefore, PMI is high although $P(t)$ is infrequent features which PMI is bias infrequent features.</p>	<p>Therefore, D-PMI is low although $P(w, R_c)$ is infrequent features which D-PMI is unbiased infrequent features.</p>

Figure 2 Comparison between PMI and D-PMI

Compare with Pointwise-mutual Information (PMI), D-PMI considers the distributions of word occurrences instead of the co-occurrence frequency between different words to avoid bias

of infrequent aspects and words. Besides, D-PMI can learn sentiment-specific words by considering the sentiment information of texts when measuring association between different lexical elements. Based on fusion sentiment lexicon, semantic orientation for each phrase calculated by D-PMI in order to improve the accuracy of classification.

Following the baseline, the method is further improved by sentiment propagation in phase 2. The review is listed under positive and negative rating rows based on their polarity but not aspect. Therefore, an unknown opinion and its neighbor explicit opinion are tending to have the same aspect and polarity based on syntactic parsing results to identify linguistic phenomena which contain strong sentiment orientations for sentiment propagation. In order to extract the sentiment relation and orientations, two rules are used for this purpose. First is two words are connected by adversative and coordinating conjunctions such as “and, or, but” follow by extracting intensifiers and diminisher are calculated. Second is that two words are connected by coordinating conjunction but there is a negation word before one of them. Finally we combine these kinds of sentiment polarity relations to from the final sentiment polarity relation score. Furthermore, we compute the sentiment relation among words for all pair of words by counting their co-occurring frequencies along with their individual frequencies which motivated by D-PMI based on their occurrence patterns. We are not only consider all the unigrams and bigrams that occur in the review, but also emphasize salient features extracted. The more frequency and occur in the reviews, the more important they are in the reviews. We model a review as bag of words and represented by a vector either unigram or bigram and have the same sentiment polarity with review and find the features from the sentiment lexicon which are similar to the features of the review, following by the

sentiment propagation. The orientation of review will be summarized and compared based on the average sentiment relation and scoring.

References

- [1] Liu, B. and Wyanne Hsu, W., “Identifying Non-actionable Association Rules.” *Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2001.
- [2] Pang, B. and Lee, L., “Opinion Mining and Sentiment Analysis.” *Journal Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval*, pp 1-135, 2008.
- [3] So Kim, M., Woo Kim, J., and Jing, C, “Comparison of Domain-Specific Lexicon Construction Methods for Sentiment Analysis.” *Advanced Science and Technology Letters*, 2016.
- [4] So Kim, M., Woo Kim, J., and Jing, C, “Comparison of Domain-Specific Lexicon Construction Methods for Sentiment Analysis.” *Advanced Science and Technology Letters*, 2016.
- [5] Srishti Sharma, “A Context Based Algorithm for Sentiment Analysis.” *International journal of Computational Vision and Robotics*, 2018.
- [6] Vinay, S. K., and Sachin N. D. “SO-PMI based Sentiment Analysis with Hybrid SVM Approach.” *International Journal of Innovation Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, 2016.